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Effect of Advanced Organizers on Academic Performance and Retention in Redox Reactions Among Secondary School Students in Port Harcourt Metropolis

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ABSTRACT

The study examined the effect of Advance Organizers on academic performance and retention in redox reaction among Secondary Schools Students in Port Harcourt Metropolis. To achieve the purpose of the study, the researcher formulated four objectives, four research questions and four null hypotheses that guided the study. The research design used was quasi -experimental design. The population for the study consisted of all 220,102 Senior Secondary School chemistry students from Port Harcourt Metropolis. Simple random sampling technique was used to select four intact classes from two schools from the target population to obtain 196 SS 2 chemistry students, 99 in the experimental group and 97 in the control group. A researched – constructed Redox Reaction Concept Achievement (and Retention) Test (RRCART) instrument, consisted of four – option 20 multiple choice items expected to measure chemistry students’ performance and retention in Redox Reactions. The instrument was validated by the researcher superior and one other senior lecturer from measurement and evaluation. The data gathered were analyzed using descriptive statistics (mean, standard deviation and percentages). Z–test statistical tool was used to test the hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance. Based on the data analysis, the findings of the study revealed that advance organizers have significant effects on students’ performance and retention in redox reaction among secondary schools students in Port Harcourt metropolis. Based on the findings, the researcher recommends that chemistry teachers should adopt advance organizer strategies for teaching of redox reactions and that the Senior Secondary School management should organize workshops for teachers on how to use advance organizer strategies.

Keywords: Advance, Organizers on Students’ Performance, Retention, Redox Reaction

INTRODUCTION

The uniqueness of chemistry makes it occupy a pride of place in the senior secondary education curriculum and it has continued to play a vital role in the economic, scientific and technological development of any nation. Chemistry as a science that underpinned most of the major discoveries of the 20th century and will continue to do so in the 21st century. Besides, its knowledge and meaningful

understanding are critical for national socio-economic development and sustainability through environmental and industrial aspect of chemistry (Matthew, 2018).

Chemistry is a branch of science that deals with the composition, properties and reactions of matter under varying conditions. Lee (2017) observed that chemistry has always been and is still a practical subject. That could be why Achimugu (2022) identified it as one of the ingredients of technology. Chemistry is defined as branch of science that deals with the study of matter, composition and properties. Anusiem (2020), defined chemistry as knowledge which relates to our everyday needs and is encountered in every field of science for solving human problems. This implies that chemistry is a central science, a human enterprise transcending all aspects of human activity and therefore plays a very crucial role in the scientific and technological development of any nation. The growing social relevance of chemical processes is evident in ageing, a lifelong consequence of oxidation, in which free radicals that are involved in the ageing process are produced and need to be removed by anti-oxidants in a reduction reaction.

Despite the low enrolment, efforts by chemistry teachers and educators to improve students' learning outcome seem not to yield positive results. Students have continued to show weakness in content knowledge and meaningful understanding of chemical concepts, leading to very poor performances in external chemistry examinations as reported in the West African Examination Council (WAEC, 2018-2022) Chief Examiner's Annual reports of the West African Senior School Certificate Examinations results in chemistry, May/June option. Analysis of candidates' performance in WASSCE Chemistry (2017-2020 May/June) indicates that it was only in 2003, 2009 and 2010 that up to 50% of the candidates had credit level and above. Results of other years showed a dwindling fluctuation in which between 30% and 49% of candidates obtained credit and above for the period under review. This poor performance of students in external Chemistry examinations has become a serious threat to our drive toward scientific and technological breakthrough.

Undoubtedly, secondary school and college students' knowledge of science is often characterized by lack of coherence and majority of the students essentially engage in rote learning due to the abstract and highly conceptual nature of science which makes it particularly difficult for students. Unfortunately, in chemistry which is widely perceived as a difficult subject due to its specialized language and abstract conceptual nature as well as the amount of content to be learnt (Gabel, 2019), the prevailing teaching methods do not actively involve students in the learning process and that seems to deprive them from taking charge of their learning.

The goal of instruction, according to Boujaoude and Attieh (2016) should be development of educational experiences that will facilitate meaningful learning and reduce rote memorization. This should deliberately stress effective knowledge transfer to the learner in the most efficient and purposeful manner. The task of the science teacher therefore is to structure students' learning, using student-centered, innovative, interactive and activity-oriented approaches that will ensure that specific aspects of concepts and principles are meaningfully learnt and internalized. This is because the most important derivatives of learning are knowledge retention and application to real life situations outside the classroom. This emphasizes the possible roles of the teachers' instructional strategy may also play in making teaching effective. This study therefore sought to investigate the effect of the intervention of advance organizers strategies in enhancing senior secondary school chemistry student's cognitive achievements and retention in redox reaction concept as determined by their own gain scores.

Concept Formation and Attainment

Concept formation relates to the way people learn to think conceptually and is a process by which people perceive sets of ideas or stimuli as related and by which they tend to put a number of instances into a class. Concept formation focuses on attributes and examples in order to reduce over-generalizations and misconceptions. It is not related to simple recall and must be constructed (Edutech, 2018).

Bruner defined concept attainment in Edutech (2018) as the search for and listing of attributes that can be used to distinguish examples from non-examples of various categories. In order to make an

accurate formation of a concept, therefore, there should be discrimination between the elements which are relevant and those which are irrelevant. For example, after observing many instances of chemical reactions, one's experience broadens, one's concept of chemical reactions widens as one learns that chemical reactions could be slow, moderately slow, very slow, fast, moderately fast, spontaneous or even explosive.

Concept of Advance Organizers Strategies

David (2020) most notable contribution for classroom application, the advance organizer, is a cognitive instructional strategy or mental learning aid is to help learners integrate new information with existing knowledge, leading to meaningful learning as opposed to rote memorization. It is therefore used to promote the learning and retention of new information. The advance organizer is an instructional strategy emphasizes the influence of students' prior knowledge on meaningful learning. As an activity-oriented strategy, it actively involves the learners in the learning process thereby enhancing meaningful understanding of concepts.

EduTech D (2018) defined an advance organizer as a cognitive instructional strategy used to promote the learning and retention of new information. It is not therefore an overview, but rather a presentation (either verbal or visual) that are 'umbrellas' for the new material to be learned, and is presented at a higher level of abstraction, generality and inclusiveness targeted at strengthening the learner's cognitive structure, Long-Crowell (2019), defined 'advance organizer as a tool to introduce the lesson topic and illustrate the relationship between the what the students are about to learn and the information they have already learned.

EduTech (2014) also defined advance organizer as information that is presented prior to learning and that can be used by the learner to organize and interpret new incoming information. The advance organizer is a strategy that the teacher uses to help students to make connections to new materials by highlighting an organizational structural patterns of the new material and their relationships to other materials already learnt. So advance organizers help teachers to fit the new information into a larger framework or existing schema to present a higher level of abstraction.

Daniel (2019) suggested that advance organizers might foster meaningful learning by prompting the student regarding pre-existing super-ordinate concepts that are already in the students' cognitive structure, and by providing a context of general concepts into which the student can incorporate progressively differentiated details. Thus by presenting a global representation of the knowledge to be learned, advance organizers might foster 'integrative reconciliation' of the sub-domains of knowledge – the ability to understand interconnections among the basic concepts in the *domain Zimmermann* (2020) opined that when students are actively involved in the learning process, they become effective in the management of their learning experiences, are self-motivated, independent and meta-cognitively active in the process of learning.

Daniel (2019) noted that advance organizers enable students to concentrate on the important concepts and provide a way of thinking that allows them to get the most out of the content, while developing their high level thinking abilities. Since advance organizers are pre-instructional strategies to activate and build schema in a cognitive learning structure, and based on the initial response to the material presented in the organizer, Daniel (2019) suggested that teachers can modify their lesson plans and the critical points that need to be covered in the materials to fit the prior knowledge of their students. This enhances the development of higher order thinking in the students, Daniel (2019) prescribed a three-phase advance organizers model of teaching in which the teacher, while using the principle of integrative reconciliation and active reception learning, can ask learners to make summaries, point out differences and relate new examples with organizers.

Redox Reaction Concept

Oxidation – reduction or redox reactions fall into a large and important group of chemical reactions that involve the movement or transfer of unobservable particles – electrons and ions – in chemical and biochemical systems. Ezirim and Mumuni (2016) that oxidation-reduction or redox reaction which

involves two opposing processes that occur simultaneously to complement one another, is a very important concept in chemical and biochemical systems and also in the senior secondary school chemistry curriculum. Lee (2017) defined oxidation as the removal of electrons from an atom and reduction is defined as the addition of electrons to an atom, and explained that electrons are lost when a substance is oxidized and electrons are gained when it is reduced.

Oxidation – reduction or redox reaction can therefore be defined as an electron bookkeeping process involving the transfer of electron(s) from one species (the reducing agent) to another (the oxidizing agent or oxidant) leading to changes in electrical charges of the species involved. The reducing agent loses electron(s) and is oxidized while the oxidizing agent or readily acquires the electron(s) and is reduced. Simply put, oxidation is the loss of electron(s) leading to an increase in the oxidation number of the species while reduction is the gain of electron(s) leading to a decrease in oxidation number of the species. These ‘charged’ species react to give rise to either desirable or undesirable products.

One important use of redox reaction concept is the provision of an electron bookkeeping device which allows for recognition of oxidation and reduction processes. The concept also provides a framework within which chemical similarities are recognized and chemical properties correlated. The understanding of chemical concepts such as redox reaction concept enhances their appreciation and consequently, their application in industry and everyday life. Besides, its role in the ageing process has led to the production of anti-oxidants (both natural and synthetic), which have helped to ameliorate some of the challenges associated with ageing.

Redox reaction, as explicated by Adesoji (2022) and Udo (2016) has posed unique and formidable challenges to students. This could be due to the students’ lack of student cognitive development and structural demands of redox reaction which perhaps could be provided by advance organizers.

Statement of the Problem

Research reports have indicated that redox reaction poses unique and formidable challenges to students. For instance, the West African Examinations Council (WAEC, 2019, 2020, 2021) Annual Chief Examiner’s reports in chemistry specifically noted that questions on redox reactions were not of popular choice among chemistry students, and those that attempted them performed very poorly (with about 32%). By implication, this may have been contributing significantly to their dismal performances in chemistry external examinations. The consistent poor performance of students in chemistry examinations is an indication that many prospective candidates may not meet admission requirements into science, medicine, engineering and technology and if this ugly trend is not checked will not augur well for our drive toward scientific and technological breakthrough and the desired application of chemistry for national economic development and sustainability will not be fully achieved. Besides, a major broad goal of the Federal Republic of Nigeria’s (FRN, 2004) National Policy on secondary education: to prepare the individual for higher education will not be attained.

Teachers rely heavily on didactic methods and teach chemistry as a body of knowledge needed only to be memorized for success in examinations and which the students usually forget afterwards. These methods do not promote higher cognitive skills in the students and have not yielded expected results especially when abstract and difficult tasks are involved. Could the poor performance of students and the difficulty experienced in learning redox reaction concept be as a result of poor and inappropriate methods used in the instructional process? What then will be the effect of the intervention of advance organizers on chemistry students’ cognitive achievements and retention in redox reaction concept? This study therefore intends to investigate the effect of advance organizers on students performance in redox reaction in secondary schools in Port Harcourt metropolis.

Purpose of the study

The main purpose of this study was to investigate the effect of Advance Organizers on students’ performance and Retention in redox reaction among Secondary Schools students in Port Harcourt Metropolis. Specifically, the objectives of the study were to:

1. Investigate the mean performance score of students taught redox reaction using Advance

- Organizers and those taught without it.
2. Examine the mean performance score of male and female students when taught redox reaction with Advance Organizers and those taught without it.
 3. Ascertain the mean retention score of students taught redox reaction using Advance Organizers and those taught without it
 4. Determine the mean retention score of male and female students taught redox reaction with Advance Organizers

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the successful conduct of the study:

1. What is the difference in mean performance scores of students taught Redox reaction using Advance Organizers and those taught without?
2. What are the mean performance scores of male and female students taught Redox reaction using Advance Organizers and those taught without it?
3. What is the difference in mean retention scores of students taught Redox reaction using Advance organizers and those taught without it?
4. What is the difference in mean retention scores of male and female students taught Redox reaction using advance organizers?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant difference in the mean performance scores of students taught redox reaction using advance organizers and those taught without advance organizer and those taught without it.
2. There is no significant difference in the mean performance scores of male and female students taught redox reaction using advance organizers and those taught without it
3. There is no significant difference in the mean retention scores of students taught redox reaction using advance organizer and those taught without advance organizer and those taught without it
4. There is no significant difference in the mean retention scores of male and female students' taught redox reaction using advance organizers.

METHODOLOGY

Quasi experimental design of non - randomized Pretest, Protest, Control group design was used for the study. It employed two separate, non-equivalent, intact senior secondary two (SS2) classes from two out of two schools that met sampling criteria. The two schools were randomly selected and assigned one experimental group and one control group. The population for this study consisted of all two hundred and twenty thousand, one hundred and two (220,102) senior secondary school chemistry students from Port Harcourt Metropolis. Out of the two hundred and twenty thousand, one hundred and two (220,102) senior secondary school chemistry students in port Harcourt metropolis, one hundred and ninety six (196) Senior Secondary two (SSS 2) students were selected from two Senior Secondary School (Port Harcourt Local Government and Obio/Akpor Local Government Area) two (SSS2) in Port Harcourt Metropolis. Simple random sampling technique through the use of balloting with replacement was used to select four intact classes from two schools (non-equivalent intact classes) from the target population to obtain one hundred and ninety six (196) SS2 chemistry students, ninety nine (99) in the experimental group and ninety seven (97) in the control group. A research-constructed Redox Reaction Performance and Retention Test (RRPRT) Instrument, consisted of four – option twenty multiple choice items expected to measure chemistry students' performance and retention in redox reactions. The original draft of the RRPRT instrument with the table of specification and lesson packages were subjected to face and content validation by the researcher's supervisors and one from measurement and evaluation Department, River State University and the other from measurement and evaluation from the Faculty of Education, Rivers state University. Their corrections, remarks and contributions were incorporated into the final form of the

instrument, which was certified adequate for the study by the researcher's supervisors and those experts. The reliability of the instrument was established based on data obtained from a trial test of RRPRT instrument on the fifty (50) senior secondary two (SS2) chemistry students from a non-participating school. This yielded a reliability co-efficient of 0.82 using Kuder-Richard's formula 20. The reliability index indicated that the instrument is valid and reliable for administration. The data collected were analyzed using descriptive statistics (mean, standard deviation and percentages) which provided answers to the research questions. Z-test statistical tool was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

RESULTS

Research Questions 1: *What is the difference in mean performance scores of students taught Redox reaction using Advance Organizers and those taught without it?*

Table 1: Mean and standard deviation analysis on the difference in mean scores of students taught Redox reaction using Advance Organizers and those taught without it.

S/N	Group / Method	Pretest			Post-test		Mean Gain
		N	\bar{X}	SD	\bar{X}	SD	
1.	Experimental Group	99	6.69	9.52	17.84	8.26	11.15
2.	Control Group	97	5.89	2.75	8.64	3.25	2.75

Source: Field Survey 2024.

The data analysis in table 1 above indicates that the mean gain of 11.15 and 2.75 was achieved between the mean performance scores of students taught Redox reaction using Advance Organizers and mean performance scores of students taught Redox reaction without Advance Organizers. This implies that there is positive and significant effect on the mean performance scores of students taught Redox reaction using Advance Organizers.

Research Question 2: *What is the difference between mean performance scores of male and female students taught Redox reaction using Advance Organizers and those taught without it?*

Table 2: Mean and Standard deviation analysis on the difference in mean scores of male students taught Redox reaction using Advance Organizers

Group	Pretest			Post-test			Mean Gain
	N	\bar{X}	SD	N	\bar{X}	SD	
Male	48	5.27	2.25	48	17.84	5.50	12.59
Female	51	6.22	3.50	51	17.84	7.25	11.62

Source: Field Survey 2024.

The data analysis in table 2 above indicates that the mean gain of 12.59 and 11.62 was achieved between the mean performance scores of male students taught Redox reaction using Advance Organizers and mean performance scores of male students taught Redox reaction using Advance Organizers. This implies that there is positive and significant effect on the mean performance scores of male students taught Redox reaction using Advance Organizers.

Research Questions 3: *What is the difference in mean retention scores of students taught Redox reaction using Advance organizers and those taught without using Advance Organizer?*

Table 3: Mean and standard deviation analysis on the difference in mean retention scores of students taught Redox reaction using Advance organizers and those taught without it

Group	Post test			Post-Post-test		Mean Gain
	N	\bar{X}	SD	\bar{X}	SD	
Experimental	99	6.69	9.52	18.07	7.25	11.38
Control	97	5.89	2.75	8.64	3.25	2.75

Source: Field Survey 2024.

The data analysis in table 3 above shows that the mean gain of 11.38 and 2.75 was achieved between mean retention scores of students taught Redox reaction using Advance organizers and mean retention scores of students taught Redox reaction without Advance organizers. This implies that there is positive and significant impact on the mean retention scores of students taught Redox reaction using Advance organizers

Research Question 4: *What is the difference in mean retention scores of male and female students taught Redox reaction using advance organizers?*

Table 4: Mean and Standard deviation analysis on the difference in mean retention scores of male and female students taught Redox reaction using advance organizers

S/No	Gender	N	Pretest		Posttest		Mean Gain
			\bar{X}	SD	\bar{X}	SD	
1.	Male (Experimental Group)	48	16.48	2.11	25.69	1.94	9.21
2.	Female (Control Group)	51	17.53	1.93	8.64	3.25	8.89

Source: Field Survey 2024.

The data analysis in table 4 above shows that the grand mean of 9.21 and 8.89 was achieved between the mean retention scores of male students taught Redox reaction using advance organizers and female students taught Redox reaction using advance organizers in their pretest and post test scores. This implies that there is positive mean retention scores of male students taught Redox reaction using advance organizers compare to the female students taught Redox reaction using advance organizers.

Hypotheses

There is no significant difference in the mean performance scores of students taught redox reaction using advance organizers and those taught without using Advance Organizers.

Table 5: Z-test analysis of significant difference in the mean scores of students taught redox reaction using advance organizers and those taught without Advance Organizers

Status	N	Mean \bar{X}	SD	Df	Std. Error	Z-cal	Z-crit	Decision
Experimental group	99	17.84	8.26	196	0.05	2.26	1.96	Accepted
Control group	97	8.64	3.25					

Source: Field Survey 2024.

The analysis on table 5 above shows that the z-cal of 2.26 is higher than the z-crit of 1.96. Therefore, the calculated z-ratio is not statistically significant at a 0.05 level of significance since it is higher than the given critical value of z-ratio. So, the null hypothesis 1 is thus rejected and the conclusion is that there is a significant difference in the mean scores of students taught redox reaction using advance organizers and those taught without it.

There is no significant difference in the mean performance scores of male and female students taught redox reaction using advance organizers and those taught without using Advance Organizers.

Table 6: Z-test analysis of significant difference in the mean scores of male and female students taught redox reaction using advance organizers and those taught without it.

Status	N	Mean \bar{X}	SD	Df	Std. Error	Z-cal	Z-crit	Decision
Male	48	17.84	5.50	99	0.05	2.24	1.96	Accepted
Female	51	17.84	7.25					

Source: Field Survey, 2024

The analysis on table 6 reveals that the z-cal of 2.24 is higher than the z-crit of 1.96. Therefore, the calculated z-ratio is not statistically significant at 0.05 level of significance since it is higher than the given critical value of z-ratio. So, the null hypothesis 2 is thus rejected and the conclusion is that there is a significant difference in the mean performance scores of male and female students taught redox reaction using advance organizers and those taught without it.

There is no significant difference in the mean retention scores of students taught redox reaction using advance organizer and those taught without using advance organizer.

Table 7: Z-test analysis of significant difference in the mean retention scores of students taught redox reaction using advance organizer and those taught without advance organizer and those taught without it.

Status	N	Mean \bar{X}	SD	Df	Std. Error	Z-cal	Z-crit	Decision
M. Experimental Group	99	18.07	7.25	196	0.05	2.26	1.96	Accepted
F. Control Group	97	8.64	3.25					

Source: Field Survey 2024.

The analysis on table 7 above shows that the z-cal of 2.26 is higher than the z-crit of 1.96. Therefore, the calculated z-ratio is not statistically significant at a 0.05 level of significance since it is higher than the given critical value of z-ratio. So, the null hypothesis 3 is thus rejected and the conclusion is that there is a significant difference in the mean retention scores of students taught redox reaction using advance organizer and those taught without advance organizer

There is no significant difference in the mean retention scores of male and female students' taught redox reaction using advance organizers and those taught with lecture method.

Table 8: Z-test analysis of significant difference in the mean retention scores of male and female students' taught redox reaction using advance organizers and those taught with lecture method.

Status	N	Mean \bar{X}	SD	Df	Std. Error	Z-cal	Z-crit	Decision
Male (Experimental Group)	48	25.69	1.94	99	0.05	2.14	1.96	Accepted
Female (Control Group)	51	8.64	3.25s					

Source: Field Survey 2024.

The analysis on table 8 reveals that the z-cal of 2.14 is higher than the z-crit of 1.96. Therefore, the calculated z-ratio is not statistically significant at 0.05 level of significance since it is higher than the given critical value of z-ratio. So, the null hypothesis 4 is thus rejected and the conclusion is that there is a significant difference in the mean retention scores of male and female students' taught redox reaction using advance organizers and those taught without it.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The findings of the study in research question one: What is the difference in mean scores of students taught Redox reaction using Advance Organizers and those taught without it reveals that use of advance organizer has significant difference in mean scores of students taught redox reaction using advance organizers than the students taught without using advance organizers. The finding of the study is in collaboration with Lee (2017) who admitted that the advance organizers is a cognitive instructional strategy used to promote the learning and retention of new information. It is usually presented ahead of a learning task at a higher level of abstraction, generality and inclusiveness, which the learner can use to organize and interpret the new incoming information and by this, the cognitive structure of the learner is strengthened (Long-Crowell, 2014). The advance organizer is therefore a means of preparing the learner's cognitive structure or frame of reference, providing a structure for students' thinking, activating the learner's conceptual pattern so that the new information can be more readily subsumed into the learner's existing cognitive structure.

The study in research questions two: What is the difference in mean scores of male students taught Redox reaction using Advance Organizers indicates that use of advance organizer has significant difference in mean scores of male students taught redox reaction using advance organizers than the students taught without using advance organizers. This study is in the same view with Santrock (2014) who observed that advance organizer is a cognitive instructional strategy used to promote the learning and retention of new information. It is not therefore an overview, but rather a presentation (either verbal or visual) that are 'umbrellas' for the new material to be learned, and is presented at a higher level of abstraction, generality and inclusiveness targeted at strengthening the learner's cognitive structure. Long-Crowell (2014) admitted that advance organizer as a tool to introduce the lesson topic and illustrate the relationship between what the students are about to learn and the information they have already learned. The author submitted that using and advance organizer to link the new information enables the learner to remember the new information more easily.

The findings of the study in research question three: What is the difference in mean retention scores of students taught Redox reaction using Advance organizers and those taught without it shows that use of advance organizer has positive difference in mean retention scores of students taught Redox reaction using Advance organizers than the students taught without using advance organizers. The finding of the study is in collaboration with Daniel (2019) who suggested that advance organizers might foster meaningful learning by prompting the student regarding pre-existing super-ordinate concepts that are already in the students' cognitive structure, and by providing a context of general concepts into which the student can incorporate progressively differentiated details. Thus by presenting a global representation of the knowledge to be learned, advance organizers might foster 'integrative reconciliation' of the sub-domains of knowledge – the ability to understand interconnections among the basic concepts in the domain. Zimmermann (2020) also opined that when students are actively involved in the learning process, they become effective in the management of their learning experiences, are self-motivated, independent and meta-cognitively active in the process of learning. Gbamanja (2019) submitted that advance organizers are frameworks that enable students learn new ideas or information and meaningfully link these ideas to the existing cognitive structure.

The study in research questions four: What is the difference in mean retention scores of male and female students taught Redox reaction using advance organizers revealed that there is positive male students' mean retention scores taught Redox reaction using advance organizers than female students taught using

advance organizers. This study is in the same view with Gabel (2019) who observed that gender is one amongst the foremost fascinating and actively debated variables in academic analysis, however with conflicting results. Adesoji (2022) have also affirmed a significant connection between students performance and gender in chemistry, particularly in favour of male. It also reported that male students have higher level of academic performance in science, technology and arithmetic than their female counterparts.

CONCLUSION

The effect of Advance Organizers on students' performance and Retention in redox reaction among Secondary Schools students in Port Harcourt Metropolis cannot be overemphasized. Based on the findings of the study, the researcher concludes that the use of advance organizer strategies enhance students' performance and Retention in redox reaction among Secondary Schools students in Port Harcourt Metropolis. The study also deduced that advance organizers is a cognitive instructional strategy used to promote the learning and retention of new information. It is usually presented ahead of a learning task at a higher level of abstraction, generality and inclusiveness, which the learner can use to organize and interpret the new incoming information and by this, the cognitive structure of the learner is strengthened and that advance organizer is therefore a means of preparing the learner's cognitive structure or frame of reference, providing a structure for students' thinking.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the researcher made the following recommendations to achieve the purpose of the study.

1. Government, through the senior secondary school management should adopt advance organizer in teaching redox reaction hence it improve the mean scores of students.
2. Senior secondary school management should organize workshop programme for teachers on how to use advance organizer strategies because it enhance mean performance scores of male students.
3. Government through the senior secondary school management should organize seminar and workshop programme for the students and teachers on effect and advantages of using advance organizer strategies hence it increase the mean retention scores of students.
4. The secondary school management should organize awareness and enlightenment campaign for the female students on the need to indicate more interest in advance organizer strategies because of its importance in the male students' mean retention scores.

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